

CULTIVATING COMMON GROUND:

Community Gardens' Potentials for Decarbonizing the Cities

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ABSTRACT

The importance of fostering connections between people and the natural world in urban environments becomes evident in radically inclusive co-productions or heterogenizing collective actions in a critical vision. In this context, the transformation of nature and culture in urban areas can be examined through the lens of resistance in urban green spaces. These spaces can be considered third natures, marginalized by the hygienic and modernization tendencies of urban policies. The practice of small-scale production in community gardens, informed by the expertise of local inhabitants, serves as a paradigm of sustainable agriculture for resilient cities. This approach reduces reliance on petroleum-based inputs and enhances soil fertility through the utilization of local methodologies. While such outcomes are more feasible in non-profit projects, similar practices can also be adopted in profit-driven initiatives when organic production proves to be economically viable. This paper explores productive community gardens known as "bostan" in Istanbul with the concept of third natures as sites of urban resilience situated between cultivated and natural environments. Also, the study reveals the future potentials of Bostan for the decarbonization of cities with the case of "Common-action Gardens" by POTplus Design Research Group, which extends the collaborative food practices and permaculture principles with innovative and technological tools.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's growing environmental problems show that relationships are produced in a non-sterile framework when designing spaces. The Anthropocene indicates that the problematic relationship between life and the environment cannot be resolved only through material issues, such as the decrease in natural resources and the increase in pollution but emphasize that cultural and aesthetic issues are also an important part of this problem. For this reason, it is important to develop a thought that questions social habits and ecological cycles. The socio-ecological perspective that emerges in this context enables the discussion of a global consensus that nature is urbanized and under threat which is limited by human control in the modern city. Therefore, the adoption of ecological policies produced for both human and non-human beings may constitute a field of action against the urbanization of nature. Away from the consensus that nature's incompatibility and need to be rescued, we need social-ecological campaigns for the formation of alternative natural imaginaries for neglected or overlooked urban areas, as joint actions with a sense of collective and democratic responsibility (Alexander, 2014), (Joachim, 2016).

In this context, Agne Denes's artwork *Wheatfield*, made in 1982, is a good example that symbolizes the fragility of the environment in the face of urbanization. Denes (2004) provoked discussions and challenged perceptions about land use, sustainability, and the relationship between nature and urban spaces that constitute globalized relations and the planet's increasingly urban environments. This idea reflects not only the great contrast between nature and the man-made environment but also a socio-ecological critique of urbanization and the desensitization of ecosystems. These types of movements respond to the mechanisms of combating a metabolic transformation through human labor for variable, unpredictable, and risky natures against increasing ecological degradation, decreasing socio-ecological opportunities and privatization of common resources (Kaika & Swyngedouw, 2011).

The concept of third nature can provide a framework for interpreting the breeding grounds of alternative life-forms where such movements emerge. As a concept introduced by architects Cristina Díaz Moreno and Efrén García Grinda (2013), third natures blur the boundaries between natural ecosystems, man-made structures, and cultural practices, with the potential to become sites of controversy in cities. They act as incubators for alternative lifestyles, fostering public dissidence, plurality, and equitable interactions beyond passive

consumption models (Moreno & Grinda, 2013). Despite their often neglected, excluded or overlooked status, these spaces can support diverse ecosystems and contribute to urban resilience by providing ecosystem services.

The article focuses on the potential for third natures to facilitate the coexistence and resilience of human activities and natural processes, drawing on design processes and political-ecological strategies. In this sense, community gardens can be regarded as a case study of third natures. The development of communal and production-oriented collective urban gardens has resulted in a hybrid of the natural, cultural, environmental and social, which has been shown to transform third natures, such as Wheatfield by Denes. This socio-ecologic transformation has been evidenced by the production of alternatives to urbanized natures that are leading to the development of responsive solutions. In addition to the mobilization of civil society in the preservation of community gardens, there is a necessity to examine their ecological potential and innovative future strategies for decarbonizing the city.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research addresses urban community gardens which remain a critical challenge in various interventions with regard to development-oriented plans of neoliberal urbanization and local governments. In the context of community gardens of this research these areas defined as third natures. The study evaluates community gardens, which serve as critical spaces for community resilience and ecological stewardship and summarizes the unique characteristics of Bostans in Istanbul and their contribution to circularity and decarbonization of cities. It then examines the Common-Action Gardens projects of the PotPLUS design group, which combine the understanding of community gardens and edible plant practices gained from Bostan with ecological stewardship, technological innovation and parametric design techniques.

3. COMMUNITY GARDENS: DECARBONIZATION BY THE THIRD NATURES

Community gardens which are physically and socially constrained by dense urbanization evolve into unique third landscapes by fostering connections between people and the natural world within urban environments. They are generally publicly owned and cultivated collectively, and they provide meeting spaces for the community, where residents can engage in civic activism through gardening, they play a critical role in connecting the residents, to the neighbourhoods they live in, and to the food they eat (Poulsen et.al., 2015; Crossan, et. al., 2016). Community-based initiatives provide food to those without access to fresh, healthy food and these systems promote alternative production networks and collective decision-making (Moreira & Morell,

2020). The creation of food commons, which encompass collective food production, preparation, and sharing, offers a potential value for the development of more inclusive, resilient, and socially vibrant urban spaces (Çersil & Kömez Dağlıoğlu, 2024). In this way, they are circular, they are based on an awareness of material cycles and material culture that support sustainable and safe production and food chains.

In a metropolis like Istanbul, community gardens situated in derelict areas of the city, which contribute to reducing the fragility of the urban system, are almost invisible as productive third nature. Historically, they are part of a movement that draws its memory from the centuries-old orchards around Istanbul. During Byzantine and Ottoman period in Istanbul, “bostan” (orchard or vegetable garden in English) where fruits, vegetables and other crops were grown within the city limits and these gardens were of vital importance in providing fresh products to the citizens. According to the definition of historian Resat Ekrem Koçu in the Istanbul Encyclopedia (1955), in history bostans are large agricultural lands or where all kinds of vegetables and fruits are grown. They are often established near waterways or rivers, in irrigated and swampy lands. However, due to urbanization and modernization in Istanbul, many of these traditional bostans have disappeared or been significantly reduced in size. While urban agriculture emphasizes the utility of urban land, it does not confront the lure of land tenure and increasing exchange value, leaving gardens vulnerable to loss amid urbanization and transformation since the 1980s (Türkkan, 2023) (Akdağ, 2016, pp. 47-62).

Bostans are historically and culturally important as they present the first examples of urban agriculture and are a source of inspiration for future applications for food flows in the city. They create a sense of ownership at the socio-ecologic level, contribute to the city’s biodiversity as permaculture, and provide local alternative economic organization (Yürük, 2017). These informal fruit and vegetable gardens have been tried to be maintained and protected with various resistances in the last decade. Some of these are perceived as areas that are currently occupied, while others are regarded as potential future locations for urban development.

It is possible to find examples of specific bostans structured with different organizational models by civil, public, and private initiatives (Durgun, 2019; Öztürk, 2020). Kuzguncuk and Imrahor are examples of neighbourhood bostans. These are common gardens with individual plots not exceeding a few square meters, allocated to neighbourhood residents by lottery each year. Yedikule, located next to the Theodosian Walls, and Piyalepaşa, next to a historical mosque, are examples of historical bostans. These are commercially productive gardens that serve as a livelihood for people. Tarlataban, located at Bogaziçi University, and Roma Bostan in Cihangir represent resistant community gardens. These gardens emerged as a new form of critical expression of the political and/or economic system following the Gezi Park movement (Table 1).

Historic bostans play an important role in the urban economy, reflecting a rare urban practice today and a tradition of small-scale vegetable production using local seeds, without pesticides and chemical fertilizers. Strategically planned community bostans use the idea of the permaculture "food forest" as a type of agroforestry system that incorporates edible plants, trees, shrubs, and vines in a design that mimics the structure and function of a natural forest ecosystem. Similarly, university based collective bostans promote sustainable production like an educational laboratory through guerrilla gardening. Engaging in collective production and observing the growth of plants have transformed public spaces from sources of stress into spaces of joy. This transformation has led to these 'third natures' being embraced and cared for, particularly by volunteers from diverse backgrounds and contexts.

KUZGUNCUK	ROMA	TARLABAN	IMRAHOR	PIYALEPASA	YEDIKULE
Neighbourhood-based	Community-based	University/student-based	Neighbourhood-based	Commercial	Commercial & historical
No sales	Sharing with community	Sharing with students	No sales	Product sale from gardens	Product sale from gardens
Social catalizer	Compost beds	Green house	Recycle of rubble	Food justice	Ruins-city walls

Table 1:
Bostans of Istanbul

While land resources in urban areas are becoming increasingly scarce, Bostans in the metropolitan city of Istanbul exemplify the principles of a circular economy through the minimization of waste, achieved through composting, upcycling of materials and water recycling. Additionally, they facilitate the regeneration of natural systems by enhancing soil health and promoting biodiversity by supporting local plant species, pollinators, and other wildlife within the urban ecosystem. These third natures serve as alternatives to capitalist privatization models while contributing to the decarbonization of urbanized environments. They achieve this by reducing the use of fertilizers, minimizing food transportation, sequestering carbon, lowering urban temperatures through vegetation, and promoting composting to decrease the amount of waste sent to landfills (figure 1).

Figure 1:
Circularity of a Bostan

In recent years, alternative food networks have become widespread, and it has become important for individuals in cities to manage their food systems in an alternative way (Michel-Villarreal et.al., 2019). In circular policies, it is important for cities to accelerate decarbonization through social interaction, sense of shared responsibility and entrepreneurial public actions (Schröder, 2022). These gardens in cities are seen to be compatible with the goals of creating areas where food is grown close to where it is consumed, reducing the environmental impact of transportation and packaging, and minimizing the carbon footprint of food systems. They offer opportunities for local governments as an inclusive social space, participatory planning and social intervention tool as well as they uphold the right to food justice that everyone has the right to access nutritious, safe, affordable and accessible food.

On the other hand, although these productive gardens cannot meet all the accessible food needs of a metropolis, it is important that they are more directly integrated into urban life with a successful governance. In the context of politics and governance, these areas are seen as empty spaces, and attempts are made to continue them on a voluntary basis, with the fear of what will happen at any moment. Many community gardens face challenges related to land tenure, as they often operate on leased or temporarily allocated urban land, making them vulnerable to displacement by urban development.

There is also a renewed interest in urban agriculture and efforts to revive bostan culture through community gardening initiatives with multidisciplinary commons. Innovative and small-scale experimental

works with a design idea explore permaculture principles and develop integrated practices that exist with different plants and animals. The POTplus Design Research Group in Turkey constructed bostan-like structures as architectural prototypes by integrating digital design and fabrication technologies with sustainable landscape issues. Their designs were called Commun-action Gardens and used by communities as urban gardens for growing, harvesting, and sharing edible plants, resting and playing, and sustaining flora and fauna (Akipek, 2019). Commun-action Gardens were featured in a series of open-air exhibitions, the 3rd International Architecture Biennial Antalya in 2015, and the Besiktas International Garden—Flower Festival Istanbul in 2016 (ibid.).

Figure 2:
Common-action Garden I
(Akipek, 2019).

Figure 3:
Common-action Garden II
(Akipek, 2019).

The gardens served as hubs for urban agriculture, growing edible plants and preserving local biodiversity by providing a space for public interaction and engagement while challenging traditional, resource-intensive landscaping methods. Advanced computational techniques were used to create modular and adaptable designs from compressed excavated soil tailored to different urban contexts, using recyclable materials such as beech marine plywood and ethylene vinyl acetate (Akipek & Yazar, 2017).

Combining the ecological possibilities of traditional materials and the productivity of community gardening into a self-functioning and reproducible system in a built and urbanized natural environment is creative and solves many design problems.

These gardens have reorganized the production methods of bostans by connecting the composting beds, tree planting areas, water basins, composite pits, seed boxes, gardening materials, animal shelters, and resting areas within a common structure. The planting of medicinal herbs and spices, the indoor drip irrigation system, and the inviting spaces for birds also demonstrate the design's concern for providing habitat for a variety of creatures. The idea embraced an open-source approach, where design elements like planting beds and compost bins were openly shared. This encouraged replication and adaptation in other contexts, amplifying the project's overall impact.

4. FINDINGS

In many years the bostans in Istanbul have become a third nature in confrontation with the state and the social and political struggle against the government or municipality's redevelopment plans. They illustrate how collective action and permaculture practices transform neglected urban spaces into living ecosystems for responsive cities. The socio-ecological actions of the bostans can be summarized by synthesizing thematic layers such as in situ ecology as efforts to heal the land; heterogeneity as diverse actors of a collective common environment. They promote circularity by increasing resource efficiency, minimizing waste, and supporting local sustainability. However, they are often influenced by political and legal processes that can introduce uncertainty and affect the stability of these initiatives. In addition, each bostan reflects its location, with production cycles that are context-specific to the unique environment and community resources in which it operates. This combination of resource management, external influences, and local adaptation shapes the functioning and impact of bostans in urban settings. These layers are related to third natures, which are complex, chaotic, often unpredictable, contingent, historically and geographically variable, reflecting a metabolic transformation by human labor as well as showing that the environment cannot be seen as a self-organizing entity.

During the pandemic, the creation of 29 collective gardens in 9 districts of Istanbul was driven by a growing awareness of the ecological crisis and a stance against authority (Özdoğan, 2023). Being community-driven and volunteer-based, key ethical and political questions arise, such as who finances the gardens, how to ensure accessibility for all, and who should be prioritized in sharing the space, all of which are essential for building solidarity. In the last decade in Istanbul, municipalities have encouraged the expansion of gardening to raise awareness about healthy food and environmental consciousness. There have been initiatives by municipalities to provide seeds, seedlings and fertilizer for rooftop gardening on the roofs of suitable public buildings or to encourage rooftop and balcony gardening on private buildings.

As active socio-ecological laboratories, bostans create a space that brings the experience of participation into the practice of life. They contribute to equitable access to fresh, healthy food, especially for urban populations who may have limited access due to socio-economic factors, and provide affordable crops harvested in dense urban environments. In this sense, permaculture seems to be an effective method for any community deprived of green spaces and left vulnerable in terms of access to food. There is no model that can be used for community gardens in every country, but the principles of permaculture represent a simple and easy practice that allows the interrelation of the networks that make up the living spaces.

In terms of learning by experience and raising awareness of sustainable food chains, innovative practices show that only a few basic interventions can create common planting areas. The examples developed by the POTplus design team encourage the practical application of the extensive knowledge of small-scale gardens. The basic needs are raised beds to provide a suitable environment for the plants, compost bins to recycle organic waste, seating to create a space for socialization and interaction, spatial orientation to ensure proper climate and air quality, and space to store tools and equipment. POTPlus' design approaches that bring these needs together reveal an innovative level with the use of digital tools in industry-university cooperation.

The given case study of a design system to integrate elements of Bostan into one continuous structure with principles of ecological design and landscape stewardship provides a space for public interaction and engagement while challenging traditional, resource-intensive landscaping methods. These practices, which create a potential public space for gathering around production and collective action in everyday parks, raise awareness of alternative methods of food production and consumption.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper evaluated Istanbul's bostans as third natures as crucial sites for fostering responsive urban communities and reimagining human-environment relationships in the face of systemic injustices. Through the lens of community gardens, the study highlights the potential for transforming neglected spaces into vibrant hubs of ecological resilience and social cohesion. Against urbanized natures, bostans emerge as socially conscious and radically circular urban commons, in a non-resource-oriented perspective, sustained through resistance, and far from the sterile framework of resource-centric viewpoints.

Developing innovative design tools to find different tools for circular resource management is important for low-carbon cities. The examined case study shows that the innovation has the potential to improve understanding of soil-related issues, identify resource

flows, make better use of existing resources, involve communities in local cycles, raise awareness about urban food systems, apply permaculture principles, and promote shared resource creation. This study demonstrates the potential of sustainable alternatives, such as urban gardens, for responsive cities that adopt a circular food system that produces healthy food locally. It reveals how existing but idle areas or sections of parks as third natures in cities can become potential for the decarbonization of future cities through architectural actions. However, it is important to involve these actions within urban policies.

It is a critical step for city authorities to recognize the importance of Istanbul's last remaining historic bostans and other agricultural areas for the preservation and decarbonization of the city. Transforming the increasingly authoritarian, growth and market-oriented management approaches of cities can be possible through alternative practices based on communal gardening. These practices can form the basis for more responsive and participatory urban policies by creating spaces for collective environmental education and social empowerment. There are many actions that can be implemented at different levels to achieve these goals. For example, activities such as organizing summer schools on gardening, identifying arable land in neighborhoods with limited access to healthy food, and holding meetings to explore the connections between the food system, nature, culture, and well-being can all be implemented. In addition, collaborating with civil society organizations in design-oriented education processes and developing architectural designs suitable for agriculture can contribute to making urban policies more sustainable and livable.

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